

D2.1

Understanding the role of digitalization and social media on energy citizenship

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Disclaimer and acknowledgement

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Executive summary

Digitalisation of energy systems has the potential to bring forth all the aspects of energy systems that can support energy citizenship behaviours and sharing of information and decision-making. However, this is premised on people being able to make sense of the information. Keeping in view this rationale, the following objectives were formulated for the current deliverable:

- To conduct interviews within energy communities to find out how information is being understood and used in the community by different types of energy stakeholders
- To identify social media content or other forms of energy-related media content that is being utilised within case study communities
- To perform topic modelling and social network analysis to identify common patterns and topics as well as identify, where possible, the factors that cause change.

This deliverable is divided into five sections. The first section is an introduction to this deliverable that gives an overview of the content. The second section is a literature review of energy citizenship, energy informatics and energy literacy. It summarises the existing body of work on these topics. The third section is about the interviews conducted with GRETA's case study representatives; it describes the interview process, questions and results. The fourth section describes the analysis of interview results using a topic modelling approach and discusses a framework for energy informatics towards energy citizenship. The fifth section discusses the role of social media in energy citizenship.

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Summary (for dissemination)	This deliverable presents (1) an analysis of the interview results conducted within the energy communities to understand how energy information is being understood and used by different stakeholders, and (2) an analysis using topic modelling to identify the role of social media in energy informatics.
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Abbreviations and acronyms

EV Electric Vehicle

Solar PV Solar Photovoltaic panel

1 Introduction

The GRETA project is funded under the call LC-SC3-CC-1-2020 topic on “Social Sciences and Humanities aspects of the Clean Energy Transition”. One aspect of this topic is to better understand how factors such as digitalisation and social media affect the emergence of energy citizenship. Digitalisation generally refers to the use of digital technologies as part of service provision. In the energy domain this often means the use of real-time data to improve energy efficiency, or improved customer interaction and services. Or else it may entail the use of energy information to develop models that support customers in decision-making, such as understanding cost-benefits of different types of solar installation or air-source heat pumps, or helping energy communities to choose appropriate green energy solutions.

The findings reported in this deliverable (D2.1) are part of the activities performed in line with WP2 objectives with a broader goal to look at how digitalisation and social media impact energy citizenship from the perspective of *energy informatics*. Broadly speaking energy informatics is the study of how energy data and information may be used to support energy efficiency measures or choices over greener energy solutions. This deliverable is related to task T2.1, which has a specific focus on the *current use* of energy information within case studies.

1.1 Overview of the deliverable

The approach taken in this deliverable has been to conduct desk research on energy informatics and how it intersects with energy literacy to potentially inform energy citizenship actions. These details are outlined in *Section 2*. This also informed the design of an interview protocol, which has been carried out with representatives from five of the GRETA case studies. The representatives were chosen from *within* the project consortium to enable the best fit between knowledge of the case study and knowledge of the GRETA project terminologies and goals; since terminology is in the process of being defined in ways that are internally consistent to the project and which are easy to communicate to a general audience, but this is not yet complete. The interviews have been analysed to understand how case studies currently utilise information and especially social media for communicating with stakeholders, including the general public. Details of the interviews and their analysis are included in *Section 3*. *Section 4* introduces some topic modelling work and relates this to the GRETA case studies. The interview results have then enabled formalisation of queries across social media content according to key topics of importance within the case studies, to better understand who is currently engaging with these topics and to assess how effectively these channels are currently working. This is described in *Section 5*.

2 Energy informatics

Ryghaug et al. (2018) have argued that energy citizenship is based on *material participation* such as purchasing solar panels or using an Electric Vehicle (EV). The premise is that the act of owning and using such items reinforces energy citizenship behaviour. A common criticism of this material view is that it may exclude those who cannot afford the technology. Further, in these cases people do not always interact with the technology directly, but instead the participation is mediated via data and other information. This might include, for example, looking at energy bills, monitoring usage through smart meters directly or investigating the long-term cost and environmental benefits of owning solar PV, air-water heat pumps, EVs and so forth. As such, this information might be used to dissuade people from participating actively. To give one example of limitations of this view, a person might decide that it is not a good investment to put a solar panel on their roof, if it is small, oriented in the wrong direction, they are not at home during the day to make use of the generated energy and the cost of battery storage is prohibitive. However, that is not to say they are not good energy citizens, if they have investigated this in the first place, or if they use this knowledge to help others make decisions on whether to get solar PV – such as advocating to a neighbour who is at home during the day, has a favourably oriented roof and who may be eligible for a grant due to their economic circumstance.

We therefore propose to look at energy citizenship from the perspective of *non-material participation*, e.g., *how engaging with energy information may or may not support decision-making and energy citizenship actions*.

We come at this from the point of view of *energy informatics*, which is a field of research that is broadly concerned with how energy information is used within energy systems to improve energy efficiency or optimise renewable energy supply. While some aspects of energy informatics concern cyber-physical systems, which are real time automated systems that use data to drive automatic responses to improve energy efficiency, we are more concerned with the role of energy informatics in human decision-making. If we take the definition of *informatics* as a field to be as follows (based on a commonly used definition with no clear source):

“Informatics harnesses the power and possibility of digital technology to transform data and information into knowledge that people use every day.”

Then we might similarly define *energy informatics* as:

“Energy Informatics harnesses the power and possibility of digital technology to transform energy data and information into knowledge that people use every day.”

Watson et al. (2010) have presented a research question matrix identifying nine important research questions concerning energy informatics. These research questions

span different stakeholders, namely suppliers, consumers, and government. Some questions from the research question matrix are more critical for energy citizenship as they deal with the concept of information that can aid citizens to be more critically informed about their energy consumption and saving. Precisely, questions such as:

1. How information systems can increase energy efficiency by integrating supply and demand data
2. How information systems can be used to change social norms around energy consumption
3. What data could aid in determining the efficiency of energy policy
4. What information can help energy citizens to understand their own energy consumption through devices that they own.

These are all important questions to look into when it comes to citizens and how they interact with energy. The authors concluded that energy informatics can help increase energy efficiency by collecting and analysing data to implement systems that can aid people to understand energy behaviour and which support optimization of energy distribution and consumption networks. Similarly, Dao et al. (2011) proposed that high level granularity of data about energy distribution and consumption will help in developing Information Systems that help in reducing energy consumption and aid sustainability (Dao et al., 2011).

In addition, other research such as Yim (2011) and Wilhite (1995) have shown that when information on energy consumption is provided (such as through energy bills or smart meters), it is effective in changing energy consumption behavior. It has also been seen that when it comes to collective culture or community wise energy projects, energy informatics have a significant role in increasing participation and engagement in energy conservation efforts, especially in communities where a strong collective culture exists.

2.1 Energy literacy definition and research

Energy literacy, very broadly, refers to the ability to answer questions and solve problems related to energy. According to the U.S. Department of Energy, who have created an energy literacy framework to support teaching and learning about energy, an energy literate person:

- can trace energy flows and think in terms of energy systems
- knows how much energy they use, for what purpose, and where the energy comes from
- can assess the credibility of information about energy
- can communicate about energy and energy use in meaningful ways
- is able to make informed energy use decisions based on an understanding of impacts and consequences.

Energy literacy is often considered as comprising three components, these are the cognitive dimension that includes the energy-related knowledge and skills as described above, the affective dimension, which includes attitudes, values, and personal responsibility towards energy and finally the behavioural dimension which relates to the intention, involvement and finally actions taken (Martin et al., 2020). There are also complex interactions between these dimensions, although as identified by DeWater and Powers (2011), energy-related behavioural and affective factors may be more closely related with each other than with knowledge. As Martin et al. (2020) also point out, most studies have shown that overall, the general population has quite low levels of energy literacy and this in turn impacts on levels of commitment towards taking energy saving measures. It is therefore clear that energy literacy may play a significant role in energy citizenship behaviours, such as being more energy efficient, purchasing EVs or solar PV and so forth. Comeau et al. (2015) explored this link in a Canadian context, through a national survey undertaken by 3000 people. Generally, they found that there was a quite good level of awareness and support for renewable energy, and for improving energy efficiency in the home but a general reluctance to take positive actions such as allowing utility suppliers to lower home or water temperatures remotely, or to install solar PV. They speculate that this could be due to a lack of detailed familiarity with these specific technologies. Similarly, they identified that Canadians were aware of ways that they could get involved in energy projects but failed to turn up to meetings, due to several factors: lack of knowledge, a feeling that their participation was tokenistic and a lack of trust in the organisations involved. Finally, they identified that most respondents favoured responsible energy use in order to protect the environment.

Resolving such issues require a multitude of approaches. In GRETA and in the work of WP2 we approach these problems by reducing barriers to engaging with energy information, so that the information derived from the data may more immediately inform and support decision-making or other energy-related behaviours. This more directly supports aspects of energy literacy related to the cognitive dimension but is also related to affective and behavioural aspects. The relationship between energy informatics, energy citizenship, and energy literacy is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between energy informatics, energy citizenship, and energy literacy (source: Ryghaug et al., 2018).

3 Interviews with case study representatives

In line with the objectives of this deliverable D2.1 identified earlier, interviews within the case study communities were conducted to understand how case studies currently utilise information and especially social media for communicating with stakeholders, including the general public. The interview protocol was based on desk research performed as part of the deliverable D2.1. There were five interviews conducted with the representatives of the GRETA case studies. The representatives were chosen from *within* the project consortium to enable the best fit between knowledge of the case study and knowledge of the GRETA project terminologies and goals. The following interview questions formed the interview questionnaire (Table 1).

Table 1: List of interview questions.

Question ID	Question statement
1	In your own words, describe your case study, community involved and the goal.
2	What information is being presented to energy citizens?
3	What channels are being used for disseminating energy information (energy bills, mobile messages, social media, website, booklets)?
4	What role (in your opinion) can digitalisation [including use of (1) social media, (2) energy platforms (energy monitoring platforms)] have in disseminating the energy information among the consumers? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Do you have any presence on social media? b. If yes, what is the primary use for social media in your case?
5	In the case study you represent, how is the energy information delivered to energy citizens? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Active: meaning systems automatically send the information based on usage and other parameters without having the user ask for the information every time. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. If so, what is the frequency? b. Passive/On Demand: the consumers must request information every time.
6	In your opinion, how has the energy information being presented to users changed their energy behaviour? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Can you give examples of any modification that was done (for example, giving relative energy consumption, energy sources, or data consumption pattern) for end users? b. Can we spot any patterns in usage from the cases where active information is delivered versus passive/on demand?
7	Have the consumers reported any gaps? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. in terms of content b. in terms of presentation/visualization. In your opinion, how should the information ideally be presented?

3.1 Interview process

Interviewees were selected from GRETA case studies. There are six case studies in GRETA. An email requesting nomination for interviewees from each case study was sent, however, only five case study representatives responded to the email and participated in the interview, this was due to one case study being potentially changed.

The interviewees were informed about the goals and objectives of these interviews at the time of seeking nomination.

All the interviews were conducted online on Microsoft Teams and were recorded for analysis purposes. Due ethical diligence was followed. It is relevant to state the consent was obtained from all interviewees before the interviews for their voluntary participation and for recording the interviews.

3.2 Interview results

Each case study representative, who took part in the interview, was deeply connected with the case study they represented and had all the necessary information about the day-to-day activities of the case study and interacted with community members regularly.

GRETA comprises of different case studies which range from co-operative societies that promote green energy consumption among communities to future ready technologies such as connected mobility which promote sustainable living and reduction of fossil fuel-based energy sources. The case studies irrespective of their demographical, social and economic conditions have one thing in common, which is encouraging citizens towards green energy transition and action. Moreover, different demographic and socio-economic details concerning each of the case studies are as follows:

1. In the case of energy community of Renewable energy district – Bologna Pilastro-Roveri, Italy (UNIBO), the neighborhood has both residential and industrial units. The residential neighbourhood has had some social problems such as substance abuse and crime and became an infamous locality. This project also aims to make it the first energy community in Italy and has support of government policies and industrial units and aims to install Solar PV panels on rooftops of households as well as industrial units.
2. In the case study named natural gas-free neighbourhoods, The Netherlands (TNO), the neighbourhood consists of both privately owned houses and housing cooperation owned dwellings. The municipality has the responsibility to convince residents to move away from natural gas-based heating to electric heating devices. This requires convincing residents to modify their residence heating infrastructure. The transition is carried out as a 9-step process where homeowners are interviewed to help them transition and their motivation for transition or barriers to transitions are identified.
3. In the case of Coopérnico – Renewable energy-driven cooperative, Portugal (CWD), the project is designed as renewable energy cooperative, and each member of the cooperative becomes a shareholding member in a social enterprise – promoting citizens involvement in the transition to a new environmental, social and economic model. It promotes collective investment in renewable energy projects and the

- sharing of benefits between its members, investors, the broader society and the environment. Coopérnico has created a large community of citizens and companies willing to contribute to a new energy, social and business model. The electricity that Coopérnico produces is integrated into the electricity grid, supplying families and businesses. Coopérnico's projects generate economic benefits, from the sale of the produced electricity, as well as environmental benefits with the production of renewable electricity and social value, either due to the close collaboration or the sharing of revenues with organizations operating in the social economy.
4. UR BEROA – Energy efficiency-driven cooperative, Spain (TEC), is an energy efficiency driven cooperative in Spain active since 1985. It focuses on the transition of household heating systems from fossil fuel consumption to greener natural gas and deals in composting and renewable energy sources such as PV cells. The co-operative is trying to evolve itself in order to decarbonize their co-operative by adopting greener sources of energy. The focus is also on using as clean energy as possible and providing the best possible service at the lowest cost. Since its inception, the cooperative has made many improvements in energy systems, such as renovating heating infrastructure and introducing smart metering. The cooperative also tries to help people avail government subsidies for energy transition and has joint ventures with other companies which provide green technology. The cooperative has many volunteers who are retired individuals.
 5. Electric autonomous and connected mobility network (TNO) – this case study is quite different from the other case studies as it looks more into the future. This case study is a part of a pan EU effort and research for transitioning to electrical vehicles devoid of any dependence on fossil fuel-based energy sources. The research focuses on how people might get involved in cooperative mobility, how cooperative mobility could lead to better safety measures, reduce accidents or reach the goal of zero accidents using autonomous vehicles in both passenger and logistical traffic. The critical component of this case study is to identify common policy goals and stakeholders, and how to implement technology. The project also identifies ecosystems of needs which include but are not limited to road redesign, new rules, new markets, new business models and to create efficiency by consuming less energy.

All the case studies have many stakeholders, such as governments who define policy framework, business entities that are based on renewable energy portfolio, local municipalities who help bring energy transition goals to neighbourhoods, and citizens who participate in green energy transition actions.

Moreover, there are many types of information that constitute the energy information available within case studies, however not all energy information is relevant to the energy citizens. For instance, technical information about energy transmission grids is not easily understood by ordinary citizens and may not be relevant information for them. During the interviews it was identified that there are certain kinds of information that *are* relevant across all case studies. These include information about policy goals and policy objectives of the transition effort. Yet there are many types of energy information that are unique to the case studies or communities the projects are

incorporated into. It was identified after the interviews that the following sets of information are more commonly being requested by citizens.

- *Why* – This set of information is about why it is important to transition to green energy sources. It is required that the case studies representatives explain and educate people about the broader goal of reduction of carbon footprint, sustainable living, and the role of brown energy in climate change and global warming. For example, the information could include how solar PV cells help reduce carbon footprint and are also a cheaper source of energy.
- *What* – This set of information is about what needs to be done to achieve the goal of living on green energy. It is required that the case studies' representatives explain what steps need to be taken to transition to green energy consumption. This could include a step-by-step guide of actions that needs to be taken, or economic and social considerations that may be relevant.
- *How* – This set of information is about how one can transition into using green energy. It is required that the case study representatives inform people about how their individual actions contribute greatly towards energy citizenship. This can be achieved by educating people to be more mindful of their energy consumption patterns, practical tips and information for residents, such as it could also include information about different subsidies or incentives that residents can avail themselves of while transitioning.

Energy information can be disseminated using many channels that can vary from the traditional to more modern methods. The channel being used depends upon the citizen who needs to be provided with such information or the type of information that needs to be presented. For instance, from the interviews it was identified that traditional methods of using flyers and posters are still quite popular and widely used as a channel to disseminate energy information. Apart from that, other channels such as radio shows, or news broadcast are at times used for this purpose. Modern channels, such as social media, are increasingly being used. During the interviews, it was identified that the case studies use varying types of channels for disseminating energy information, which include:

- Flyers
- Interpersonal Meetings
- Townhall Meetings
- Newsletters and Magazines
- Website / Blogs
- Social Media
- Radio and Television

Furthermore, respondents in the interviews have opined that energy information systems have been useful in advancing the concept of energy citizenship by increasing the insight into citizen's energy consumption pattern and driving up citizens' engagement on this topic. Energy information systems' usefulness depends upon the message they convey and the kind of demographic they are catering to. Energy

information systems could also help in visualization of energy information. It allows the circulation of up-to-date information. Yet, there is room for improvement in this regard.

4 Energy informatics framework for energy citizenship

This section aims to analyse the existing viewpoints on the current ways of presentation and representation of energy information across the GRETA case studies, and then evaluate them against a hypothetical backdrop associated with the optimal representation of such information using energy-related digital platforms. The core idea behind this exercise was to give visibility to the potential shortcomings and best practices related to the presentation and representation of energy information in the GRETA project.

For that, the open-ended, unstructured answers to questions 4-5-6-7 represented a fruitful textual source of evidence about the existing best practices and gaps on this theme across all GRETA case studies. Therefore, a rigorous text classification was performed on these unstructured texts, using a method entitled topic detection (also known as topic modelling or topic analysis), following a similar methodological approach performed by Klein et al. (2021). Through this method, it was possible to break down, extract, and categorise the most relevant parts-of-speech tags or key phrases from textual data into topics that summarise its core ideas, giving a complete picture of the topics discussed in a text corpus.

Furthermore, considering that the dataset contained in questions 4-5-6-7 was not overly extensive, the topic detection was carried out manually with a proper level of accuracy and efficiency, which allowed to derive meaning and reveal patterns across the interviewed multiple viewpoints on the current way of presentation and representation of energy information in GRETA. This approach is in line with the criteria set by Podger et al. (2012) with regards to the design of context-appropriate assessment methods and tools, which includes: (i) methodological rigour, richness, and reliability of results; (ii) adaptability to the target respondents and project specificities; (iii) ease of use resources for replicability.

Specifically, the content of these open-ended answers was categorised into seven different gap-oriented topics (i.e., things that should be improved) and eight best practice-oriented topics (i.e., things that are currently done well). The correlation between these topics and their corresponding answers are presented in Table 2, together with the frequency in which these topics appeared across the interviewed answers.

Table 2: Topic detection exercise across all GRETA case studies.

Topic Interpretation	GRETA Case Study					Frequency
	<i>Pilastro-Roveri</i>	<i>Natural Gas-Free Neighbourhood</i>	<i>Coopérnico</i>	<i>UR BEROA</i>	<i>Connected Mobility</i>	
Gap-oriented topics (i.e., what should be improved)						
Ease-of-use, intuitive presentation/ visualisation of energy information	Q4: "Energy Monitoring platform could go a long way to communicate and visualise the information"	Q4: "Energy information could also help in visualisation of energy information"	Q7: "(...) they can't take advantage of the information presented - they don't know how to work with it, and they don't have interest despite being an easy way to obtain data"		Q5: "Platforms exist but less aware, consume time, need to know something about technology"	80%
Simplification of complex/ overly technical information	Q7: "(...) easily explaining the benefit of the result to individual" Q4: "If energy information systems are made easy to understand and use, they are useful"	Q4: "Less of technical and more easily understandable content"	Q7: "Information is not always easy to comprehend, that is, even if you try to simplify the content, there are situations in which you really have to talk to people"	Q6: "Information needs to be very clear, and information should be simplified" "Consumer don't understand technical information of energy bill"		80%
Reduce overload of information			Q7: "(...) a lot of information in one document, e.g., invoices. They must have so much information that people sometimes give up trying to understand"		Q4: "As citizens use fully automated vehicle, people they will have more time, they will have mobile and internet, and it will create more data. Could create many services for user and risk and opportunities for manufacturer"	40%
Inclusive, non-discriminatory		Q4: "Energy information systems would"		Q4: "(...) generational gap due to old"		40%

information sharing		be useful depending upon the message they convey and the kind of demographic they are catering to"		age, thus communication strategy is still old fashion"		
Awareness raising					Q7: "Media shows sense of urgency, but it does not translate to immediate consumption changes. Rebound effect over consumption. More awareness"	20%
Retain attention			Q7: "(...) the problem here is after the activation phase (within the engagement process) where there is loss of interest in the platform (after 2 months it's not interesting anymore)"			20%
Catering of trustworthy and scientifically valid information		Q7: "Some problems municipality officials face due to social media disinformation as residents believe in wrong information at times. Municipalities need to step in shoes of citizens and cater to information that they need to make transition plan a success"				20%

Best practice-oriented topics (how it should ideally be done)						
<p>Humanisation of processes / spur social value generation</p>		<p>Q6: "What we have seen in case studies that have been successful in involving people from start or involving people the way they feel comfortable with, is making it possible to have discussion with homeowners and talk about their worries and needs"</p> <p>Q6: "How to be involved and feeling of being included in process (This is more important, that people have feeling of being included and be a part)"</p> <p>"Trust is important, technology is secondary"</p> <p>"Most people do not care about heat transition from natural gas to electric one, thus you must tailor the information and link it to things which people care about, to be able to get them on board"</p>	<p>Q6: "Members had doubts about the indexed tariff and therefore Coopérnico needed to explain what consumption profiles, tariff components, etc. were. Example of Catarina as a member: the 1st time she felt the need for more information, she called and there was another person on the other end of the line (staff, not volunteer). She even found this strange (i.e., positively impacted) for not being a standard call center call. Basically the modus operandi is members working for members"</p>			<p>40%</p>

Use of graphs/ images			Q7: "(...) images or graphics are much easier to understand - e.g., the newsletter"			20%
Digitalisation/ dematerialisation of information and processes				Q4: "Room for improvement on digitisation" Q4: "Digitisation of relationship with member including billing and communication"		20%
Use of metrics to present information	Q7: "Metrics that could denote consumption and benefits at individual and social level"					20%
Create step-by- step guidelines	Q7: "Clear information on concrete steps to take"					20%
Create new communication streams				Q4: "New communication strategy and technology needs to be further adopted"		20%
Associate processes with a monetary value	Q7: "Information about monetisation of the effort that would require individual to best behave towards energy"					20%
Personalisation of the presentation of information		Q4: "As people move up the steps in customer journey, the questions change from more general to more specific"				20%

In the same line of thought as Klein et al. (2021), it is important to note that the topic detection exercise was interpretative and adopted a social constructionist perspective.

Hence, the interpretations made cannot be understood as definitive given that the proposed approach deals with uncertainty, multiple perspectives, and the absence of a single, universally valid answer to the topic detection exercise – i.e., they should be open to multiple rounds of reinterpretation.

The analysis of Table 2 revealed answers that were clearly articulated, multifaceted, and rich in details and complexity, often with a strong view on the existing shortcomings in each case study, as well as a pragmatic view on how things should be ideally done in a best-case scenario. This is evidenced in the examples showcased below:

“Most people do not care about heat transition from natural gas to electric one, thus you must tailor the information and link it to things which people care about, to be able to get them on board”

“(…) Basically (Coopérnico’s) modus operandi is members working for members”

This indicates that the interviewed could make sense of a complex social dimension, suggesting a strong commitment, knowledge, and real interest in their respective case study.

Furthermore, some topics stood out from others as they represented shared gaps and best-practices across multiple case studies – e.g., the need for (i) ease-of-use, intuitive presentation/ visualisation of energy information; and (ii) simplification of complex/ overly technical information, which was present in 80% of the interviews (i.e., in 4 out of 5 interviews). These topics that were transversal to different case studies are exceptionally valuable given that each interview was conducted individually (and without any connection to the other interviews) as to avoid conformity bias. Hence, a common thread binding different case studies was detected, even though they highly differ from one another (in terms of scales, geographic locations, legal frameworks, energy community configurations, sociodemographic characteristics, sociotechnical infrastructures, climate zones, etc.).

Based on the above analysis, it can be assumed that the interviewed proposed valid gap- and best practice-oriented recommendations that could be translated into the proposal of embedded social mechanisms in the design of energy-related digital platforms.

Nonetheless, given that the topic exercise was solely based on the interviewed persons’ self-reported data, and in view to maintain a certain degree of “reflectiveness” about the proposed evaluation, it is essential to note that the interview responses might present some degree of Hawthorne effect – which stands for the idea that individuals (i.e., the interviewed) might modify some aspects of their behaviour (i.e., their answers) due to their awareness of being observed (i.e., interviewed).

Ideal presentation of energy information using energy-related digital platforms

This section aims to present a hypothetical backdrop associated with the optimal representation of energy information by the use of energy-related digital platforms, and then compare it with the gap- and best practice-oriented topics uncovered in the previous section to see how deeply they correlate. Ideally, the uncovered topics might be suggestive of potentially new end-user engagement mechanisms to be embedded in the design of energy-related digital platforms.

For that, the work previously carried out in the DOMINOES project and the Flexigy project (related to the design of user-centric frontend local energy market interfaces for end-user interaction) was used as the starting point for the understanding of such hypothetical ideal backdrop, as it was highly informative on how to practically merge Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH) knowledge into the design of energy-related digital tools. It is worth noting that the DOMINOES user-centric frontend interface component design was further expanded/improved in the Flexigy project, given that both projects shared similar objectives with regards to this specific theme.

In any case, the DOMINOES work (and by extension, the Flexigy work) was described by Annala et al. (2021), and the main takeaways from this study were filtered here. Namely, the core scientific fundamentals from the SSH that informed the development of the proposed user-centric frontend local energy market interfaces for end-user interaction were:

- The provision of added value (e.g., in the forms of data privacy, data security, comfort gains, financial incentives, information services); the identification of different end-user typologies; promotion of capacity building and awareness raising; creation of commitment and appeal; delivery of effective feedback and pricing schemes; promotion of a variety of end-user interaction schemes; ease-of-use and intuitive designs; incentivisation of social comparison; and stimulation of reflection and learning;
- Focus shift from the individual to the energy community level to account for the socially grounded nature of humankind, given that energy communities can often offer solutions to collective problems that are not addressed at the individual level. Examples include social dilemmas (e.g., seeing others doing their part); social conventions (e.g., join new social groups that present alternative social conventions that challenge existing ones); socio-technical infrastructures (e.g., experimentation beyond conventional solutions); and helplessness (e.g., end-user empowerment via collective actions toward common goals);
- In terms of energy reporting interfaces to drive behaviour change: feedback frequency; different measuring units for different targeted end-user groups; data granularity; balance between pull and push (i.e., what is solicited from and displayed to end-users); appropriate selection of the presentation medium; location of the energy reporting system; appealing visual design and language of the end-user interface; suggested actions and solutions; comparison; and information sharing.

- Leverage game-based approaches to stimulate decision-making processes in synchronism with market rules and pricing signals and using gamification components and game elements (feedback and points being the most used, respectively) in mobile energy-related applications to drive their uptake.
- Use of visual means and contextual information over abstract information, as well as community-wide information rather than household-level.

Based on the suggestions collected across the SSH literature on the design of user-centric frontend interfaces for end-user interaction, the DOMINOES / Flexigy project conceptualised and designed an optimal local energy market interface to spur end-user interaction within a virtual local energy market ecosystem [i.e., an ecosystem where they could interact and transact their energy assets (e.g., energy flexibility, peer-to-peer energy sharing, etc.) with other market participants within the same energy community in a proactive way].

Therefore, it becomes necessary to specify the tools, functionalities, resources, virtual modules, as well as the general aesthetics of the user-centric frontend virtual interfaces that were optimally designed to enhance a simplified user experience and attract and retain the attention of the energy community members in the DOMINOES / Flexigy Marketplace. In view of that, some highly detailed static representations and descriptions of the final five modules of the Flexigy Marketplace frontend virtual interface for energy community members are given below:

- Account Settings module (Figure 2): This module was designed so that end-users can enter and manage their personal information in the Flexigy Marketplace, such as their full name, address, phone number, email, energy contract details (energy distributor, energy tariff, contracted power, etc.). In addition, end-users can configure their virtual public profile on the Flexigy Marketplace just like any other social media channel (i.e., choose a public photo, configure their username, provide a brief description of themselves to others, etc.), as well as define which services they want to provide or request on the local energy market (i.e., whether they want to participate in the peer-to-peer energy sharing market or the energy flexibility sales market). Such measures are essential to comply with privacy and data security requirements, as they preserve the real identity and personal data of users in the local energy market.

Figure 2: Visual representation of the Flexigy Marketplace Account Setting module.

- Dashboard (Marketplace Overview) module (Figure 3): In this module, end-users can view real-time data or historical data about the local energy market, such as statistics on the prices of services transacted in this market (for example, purchase/sale prices of the energy transacted in the peer-to-peer energy sharing market, sale price of the KWh transacted in the energy flexibility market, price of purchase of energy from the grid, etc.). In addition, the module shows information on the energy use profile categorised by source (i.e., how much energy came from the distribution network and how much electricity consumed came from local production of renewable sources in the local energy market), allowing users to understand their energy autonomy as soon as possible. This information can be aggregated or disaggregated according to specific needs, from hourly data to annual data. This information can also be presented in terms of € or KWh.

Figure 3: Visual representation of the Flexigy Marketplace Dashboard module.

- Peer-to-Peer Energy Sharing (Sale module) (Figure 4): In this module, producers can monitor their distributed generation and compare it with their energy consumption in real-time and historically, thus being able to identify in which times there was excess generation of renewable energy, using different time windows (i.e., from hourly data to annual data). This information can also be presented in terms of € or KWh. A side tab provides summary information about the revenue from the sale of this renewable generation surplus in the local energy market, either in terms of € or KWh, as well as the fluctuation in the price of transacted energy in several time windows. Furthermore, in this module, producers can set monetary and non-monetary limits for the sale of their surplus generation by selecting predefined behavioural sales profiles, including:
 - Go-Ahead Profile: for suppliers who want to sell all of their renewable electricity generation in the local energy market - that is, without self-consumption
 - Tactical profile: for suppliers who only intend to sell their surplus renewable generation in the energy market - that is, excess of renewable electricity generation after self-consumption
 - Selective profile: for suppliers who wish to sell their renewable generation surplus only to specific end-users (e.g., for neighbours only; for friends/family within the same energy community, etc.)
 - Altruistic profile: for suppliers who wish to donate free of any cost their surplus renewable generation to those in a situation of energy deficit / socio-economic disadvantage / energy poverty.

This module also features a smart, bespoke social matchmaking engine that creates compatible matches between energy suppliers and energy buyers in peer-to-peer energy sharing services, based on their predefined behavioural profiles and other variables (e.g., forecasting energy consumption profiles, renewable generation profiles, battery storage capacity and energy prices in local and wholesale energy markets). This automation is designed to alleviate the burden on participants of having to make constant decisions regarding the purchase and sale of energy in the Flexigy Marketplace.

Figure 4: Visual representation of the Flexigy Marketplace Peer-to-Peer Energy Sharing (Sale module).

- Peer-to-Peer Energy Sharing (Purchase module) (Figure 5): In this module, energy purchasers partaking in the peer-to-peer energy sharing market have the option to choose between three different behavioural purchase profiles based on the specific trading behaviour they want to assume in the local energy market (which nonetheless can be changed whenever desired), including:
 - Bold profile: for buyers who want to maximise their consumption of renewable energy regardless of the electricity price transacted in the local energy market
 - Cautious profile: for buyers who wish to purchase renewable generation in the local energy market only when the price is lower than the price of energy coming from the grid
 - Community Supporter profile: for buyers who only wanted to purchase renewable generation from specific suppliers in the local energy market.

This module was designed to include a smart, bespoke social matchmaking mechanism that creates compatible matches between energy buyers and suppliers in peer-to-peer energy sharing services, based on their predefined behavioural profiles and other variables (e.g., end-users’ profile selection; day-ahead forecasting of energy consumption profiles, renewable generation profiles, battery storage capacity; and energy prices in the wholesale and local energy markets). This automation is designed to alleviate the burden on participants of having to make constant decisions regarding the purchase and sale of energy in the Flexigy Marketplace – thus representing a valuable and resourceful tool for those who wished to have a more proactive role in the local energy markets, but who had a misleading perception that such a role was too difficult or cumbersome.

In addition, this module presents an interactive map where the energy buyer can see all available energy suppliers from the local energy market grouped by region. When the map is zoomed in on a specific region, the energy supplier clusters are ungrouped, and each supplier is identified and listed individually in a side tab (according to their virtual public profile previously defined in the account setting module). The energy buyer can only see the approximate location of their suppliers on the map without accurate precision (i.e., within a given radius), in order to ensure compliance with privacy and data security protocols.

Figure 5: Visual representation of the Flexigy Marketplace Peer-to-Peer Energy Sharing (Purchase module).

- Energy Flexibility Service Provision module (Figure 6): This module was designed so that end-users can market and monetise the flexibility of their flexible

home devices in the Flexigy Marketplace. The purchase of this unbundled flexibility is mediated by the energy aggregator, which manages the aggregated flexibility plans to meet the specific needs of several different actors in different energy market levels.

In this module, each end-user must select which flexible residential devices they want to include in the energy flexibility sales market. Once selected, it is necessary to configure the consumption profile of each one of them so that they can be included in the market. To avoid the arduous task of manually configuring each flexible device one by one, an intelligent automated configuration mechanism has been devised. This mechanism assesses the energy consumption profile of each selected device in a disaggregated and automated way (through real-time monitoring and control), creating an individual flexibility offer profile for each device. This set of different disaggregated flexibility offers is then aggregated into flexibility plans based on several different variables, such as future consumption forecasts, renewable generation, storage capacity of static or automotive batteries, as well as forecasts of purchase requests for flexibility of several different participants in order to estimate the potential to respond to these specific market requests.

Furthermore, a side tab shows a history of the overall remuneration of sales of the flexibility from energy assets both in € and KWh, as well as the end-user's individual performance in monetising their flexibility in various time windows.

Figure 6: Visual representation of the Flexigy Marketplace Energy Flexibility Service Provision module.

- Reward module (Figure 7): This module was designed to show the monetary and non-monetary rewards accumulated by the end-user according to their level of interaction and participation in the local energy marketplace. Illustratively, the top left tab of this module shows the end-user's overall financial gains through the participation in energy flexibility services and peer-to-peer energy services. This number is analysed against several different milestones, which allows end-users to earn different recognitions based on merit (e.g., points, leaderboard position, badges / achievements, etc.), and non-monetary awards. To further encourage their involvement, users can see how much effort is still needed to reach the next milestones.

Figure 7: Visual representation of the Flexigy Marketplace Reward module.

By analysing the abovementioned information against the foundational core constructs raised from the SSH literature, and by comparing it with the gap- and best practice-topics identified in the previous section, it becomes clear that the DOMINOES/Flexigy Marketplace platform provides an ideal (although hypothetical) virtual ecosystem to spur end-user engagement in local energy markets/energy communities and, by consequence, to foment the energy citizenship phenomena. An important argument to be made here (perhaps the most important one) is that, in order to strive and succeed in the optimal design of energy-related digital platforms, it is fundamental to surpass formal boundaries of techno-economic constructs, and start also addressing qualitative, subjective constructs, such as emotions, affections, and feelings – touching in that sense the concept of “*corazonar*” (also known as warming up of reason) proposed by Santos (2018).

5 Role of social media in energy informatics

Social media is an important tool for disseminating energy information, however the use of social media is generally limited to younger population and many individuals do not use social media due to generational gaps (Correa et al., 2010). Furthermore, concerning the use of social media for disseminating energy information, it was identified during the interviews that the problem of misinformation persists and could hinder the advancement of energy citizenship.

To identify more details on this, an online tool Hastagify.me was used to analyse Twitter trends for energy related hashtags. This tool was selected from many other similar online tools as this tool can analyse the engagement and popularity of a topic through hashtag search. Hashtags were used because they collect different content under the same group based on the hashtag used with it. This helps to consider all the tweets that were made using the same hashtag or its slight variations. For instance, #cleanenergy, #renewableenergy, #energy, #solarenergy, #greenenergy, #sustainability, and #energytransition were analysed using the online tool. These hashtags were chosen based on words used by the interviewees and have relevance to the topic considered in this deliverable. English was used as translating between languages can lead to errors if the researcher is not proficient in that language and since the language of interviews was English.

As a result of the analysis, using the tool for the last 8 weeks' worth of tweets, Figure 8 for instance shows that there is a lot of variation in popularity of these hashtags, and the popularity score is less than 50 compared to the most popular hashtag in Figure 9 which has a popularity score of 100. The popularity score is based on the velocity with which new tweets are posted on Twitter all over the world. Using the same tool, *it was revealed that the tweets or content posted on Twitter using such hashtags do not generate much engagement from people, as the number of likes and comments on the content are mostly absent, except for few exceptions when the content is posted by a celebrity user. For example, the most influential person using the #cleanenergy hashtag or #energytransition hashtag is the Hollywood celebrity Leonardo DiCaprio.*

Figure 8: Popularity trend of analysed hashtags on Twitter.

However, some of the recent trends on Twitter with high popularity indices using the same tool are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Recent trends on Twitter with the list of top hashtags.

It can therefore be concluded that the role of social media – at least as pertaining to Twitter – in energy informatics is yet to be exploited to its full potential, and this

requires (1) efforts on the part of all stakeholders to use social media for disseminating energy information that aids towards energy citizenship, (2) formulating a coordinated response strategy for dissemination of energy related content while exploiting the social media to its fullest potential. For instance, the top trend of #JusticeforRailwayStudents is a coordinated Twitter campaign run by students from India who want the government to roll back their decision on recruitment by state run transportation (Justice for Railway Students | Demands of Railway Aspirants, 2021). Therefore, social media can be exploited to its full potential if all stakeholders use social media with a coherent strategy towards information dissemination.

6 Summary and key takeaways for GRETA

This deliverable D2.1 has aimed to understand how people use energy related information to inform energy citizenship actions. We consider this from a perspective of 1) energy informatics – which harnesses the power and possibility of digital technology to transform energy data and information into knowledge that people use every day, and 2) energy literacy – especially related to how well people can make sense of this information and use it to answer questions and solve problems related to energy. Research has shown that energy informatics can have a positive effect on energy conservation actions under certain circumstances, but there are still open questions about what information to use and when or how it should be presented to different stakeholders and how this relates to individual or collective energy literacies.

Through case study interviews we have identified three types of information that are useful to citizens to engage them with energy citizenship actions. This includes information about *why* the green transition is important, *what* actions can be taken and *how* citizens can get involved. However, by analysing the case study interviews we also identify that there is still work to be done in making energy information easy to use, especially by a general audience. Further, by reflecting on some prior research we find that in addition to being understandable we might also consider the emotive aspects of information as being also important in fostering energy citizenship. This aligns well with our proposed link between energy informatics and energy citizenship via energy literacy, since this takes into account not just the cognitive but also the affective aspects of energy literacy and their relation to behaviour and action. In this regard, we have also identified that the socio-economic condition of a neighbourhood changes the information needs, for example a more affluent neighbourhood may be less concerned about the economic costs of transition whereas in more impoverished neighbourhoods there is understandably more concern about costs. Such considerations could be presumed to have an effect on the affective dimensions of energy literacy, such as they relate to people's attitudes and values, yet more research needs to be done to better understand such a relationship.

Finally, where some energy information is delivered through dedicated channels or interfaces, we are also interested in how social media might be a tool for energy citizenship. In this regard, we identified that in addition to concerns about social media potentially spreading misinformation, the current impact of social media on energy related topics is not as strong as it could be.

This deliverable will help to guide GRETA's case study implementation and analysis (deliverables D1.3 and D1.4) as well as support creation of design principles for energy interfaces based on energy informatics (D2.4).

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